

[white paper]

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Mathematical Art: Insights and Tricks

Open Mathematics Collaboration*

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Abstract

This collection features ingenious insights from theorems in pure mathematics alongside practical techniques employed in applied mathematics.

keywords: mathematical tricks, insights, pure mathematics, applied mathematics, formulas

The most updated version of this white paper is available at
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Preamble

1. *It's my view that contemplating the beauty of those mathematical drawings can enhance the mathematical maturity of the truth-seeking observers.*

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Introduction

2. Throughout my studies in both theoretical physics and pure mathematics, I have gathered this collection of mathematical results [1–5].
3. The mathematical insights in this paper were derived from theorem proofs across various areas of mathematics.

Notation

4. $\delta(x) :=$ Dirac function
5. $\delta_{ss'} :=$ Kronecker delta
6. $\Theta(t) :=$ Heaviside step function
7. $F_i :=$ i -th term in the Fibonacci sequence
8. $F'_n :=$ n -th Fermat number
9. $n \in \mathbb{N} = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$, $\mathbb{N}_0 = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$
10. $\text{gcd} :=$ greatest common divisor
11. $A, B, C, X, Y, W, Z :=$ sets
12. $\mathcal{P}(A) :=$ powerset of A
13. $0.a_0a_1a_2\dots :=$ binary expansion of $a \in [0, 1)$
14. $\sim :=$ equinumerous
15. $\cong :=$ bijection
16. $p :=$ prime number
17. $p_n :=$ n -th prime number
18. $f, g, h :=$ functions
19. $\underline{\vee} :=$ exclusive or
20. $\mathbb{P} :=$ set of prime numbers

Nomenclature

21.

$$\text{nabla (del)} : \nabla = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \hat{i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \hat{j} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \hat{k}$$

22.

$$\text{Laplacian} : \nabla^2 = \Delta = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2}$$

Insights in Pure Mathematics

23.

$$f : A \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(A), \quad B = \{a \in A \mid a \notin f(a)\}$$

24.

$$f : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N}) \rightarrow [0, 1), \quad f(A) = 0.a_0a_1\dots, \quad a_n = \begin{cases} 0, & n \notin A \\ 1, & n \in A \end{cases}$$

25.

$$a \in [0, 1), \quad 0.a_0a_1a_2\dots, \quad g(a) = \{n \in \mathbb{N} \mid a_n = 1\}$$

26.

$$a < b \rightarrow a \leq b$$

27.

$$B = \bigcup \{\mathcal{P}_n(\mathbb{N}) \mid n \in \mathbb{N}\}$$

28.

$$f : A \rightarrow B, \quad g : C \rightarrow D, \quad h : A \times C \rightarrow B \times D, \quad h(a, c) = (f(a), g(c))$$

29.

$$\mathbb{P} = \{P_n \mid n \in \mathbb{N}\},$$

$P_n :=$ set of natural numbers ending with exactly n zeros,

$\overbrace{m, n} :=$ natural number with m ones and n zeros

(example: $\overbrace{3, 1} = 1110$),

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N} : A_n = \{\overbrace{m, n} \mid m \in \mathbb{N}\},$$

$$f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{P}, f(n) = P_n$$

30.

$$A \sim B, h : A \cong B, F : \mathcal{P}(A) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(B),$$

$$\forall X \in \mathcal{P}(A) : F(X) = \{h(a) \mid a \in X\}$$

31.

$$f : \mathbb{R} \cong (0, \infty), f(x) = 2^x, g : (0, \infty) \cong (0, 1), g(x) = \frac{1}{x^2 + 1},$$

$$h : (0, 1) \cong (a, b), h(x) = (b - a)x + a$$

32.

$${}^{\mathbb{N}}\mathbb{N} = \{f \mid f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}\}, {}^{\mathbb{N}}\mathbb{N} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N})$$

33.

$${}^X Y = \{f \mid f : X \rightarrow Y\}, {}^{\mathbb{N}}\{0, 1\} \subseteq {}^{\mathbb{N}}\mathbb{N}$$

34.

$$m = p_1 p_2 p_3 \dots p_n + 1$$

35.

$$F'_n = 2^{2^n} + 1, n \in \mathbb{N}_0,$$

$$(n \geq 1) : \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} F'_k = F'_n - 2$$

36.

$$2^p - 1$$

37.

$$\Pi(x) = \#\{p \leq x : p \text{ is prime}\}, x \in \mathbb{R}$$

38.

$$x = (n + 1)! + 2$$

39.

$$h = g^{-1} \circ f$$

40.

$$N_{a,b} = \{a + nb : n \in \mathbb{Z}\}, \quad a, b \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad b > 0,$$

$O \subseteq \mathbb{Z}$ is open if $O = \emptyset \vee (\forall a \in O \exists b > 0 : N_{a,b} \subseteq O)$,

$(O_1, O_2 \text{ are open, } a \in O_1 \cap O_2, N_{a,b_1} \subseteq O_1, N_{a,b_2} \subseteq O_2) \rightarrow$

$$\rightarrow (a \in N_{a,b_1 b_2} \subseteq O_1 \cap O_2),$$

$N = \{\emptyset, \mathbb{Z}, O_1, O_2, O_3, \dots\}$ is a topology on $\mathbb{Z}$,

$$N_{a,b} = \mathbb{Z} \setminus \bigcup_{i=1}^{b-1} N_{a+i,b}, \quad \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{1, -1\} = \bigcup_{p \in \mathbb{P}} N_{0,p}$$

41.

$f : A \rightarrow B, \quad g : B \rightarrow A, \quad A = X \cup Y, \quad X \cap Y = \emptyset,$

$$B = W \cup Z, \quad W \cap Z = \emptyset,$$

$$W = f(X) = \{f(x) \mid x \in X\},$$

$$Y = g(Z) = \{g(z) \mid z \in Z\}$$

42.

$$2d(x, y) = d(x, y) + d(y, x)$$

43.

$$Y_d = Y \cup \{d\}$$

44.

$$x \in A \rightarrow x \in A \cup B$$

45.

$\{[0, 1)\}, \{[0, 1/2), [1/2, 1)\}, \{[0, 1/4), [1/4, 1/2), [1/2, 3/4), [3/4, 1)\}, \dots$

Techniques in Applied Mathematics

46.

$$\frac{n+1}{n} = \frac{1 + \frac{1}{2n+1}}{1 - \frac{1}{2n+1}}, \quad \frac{1}{n(n+1)} = \frac{1}{n} - \frac{1}{n+1}$$

47.

$$2^n n! = (2n)!! = 2 \cdot 4 \cdot 6 \dots (2n)$$

48.

$$\frac{(2n)!}{2^n n!} = (2n-1)!! = 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 7 \dots (2n-1)$$

49.

$$f(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} F(\omega) e^{i\omega t} d\omega, \quad F(\omega) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(t) e^{-i\omega t} dt$$

50.

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{d^m}{dx^m} [\delta(x)] f(x) dx = (-1)^m \frac{d^m}{dx^m} f(0)$$

51.

$$f(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(x-x_0)^n}{n!} \left. \frac{d^n f(x)}{dx^n} \right|_{x=x_0}$$

52.

$$D^n(AB) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} D^{n-k} A D^k B$$

53.

$$\sum_{n=1}^N n \cdot n! = (N+1)! - 1$$

54.

$$\int_0^{+\infty} x^2 e^{-\beta x} dx = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \beta^2} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\beta x} dx$$

55.

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-x^2} \cos(ax) dx = \operatorname{Re} \left[\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-x^2} e^{iax} dx \right]$$

56.

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-x^2} \sin(ax) dx = \operatorname{Im} \left[\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-x^2} e^{iax} dx \right]$$

57.

$$e^{-x^2+iax} = e^{-(x-\frac{ia}{2})^2} e^{\frac{a^2}{4}}$$

58.

$$\int x e^{-\beta x^2} dx = \int e^{-\beta x^2} d\left(\frac{x^2}{2}\right)$$

59.

$$0.999\,999\dots = 1$$

60.

$$ax^2 + bx + c = a(x - z_1)(x - z_2)$$

61.

$$n \geq 1: p(x) = a(x - z_1)(x - z_2)\dots(x - z_n)$$

62.

$$1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} + \dots > \frac{9}{10} + \frac{9}{10} + \frac{9}{10} + \dots$$

Aleph

63.

$$\aleph_0 + 1 = \aleph_0, \quad \aleph_0 + \aleph_0 = \aleph_0$$

64.

$$2^{\aleph_0} = \aleph_1 > \aleph_0$$

Binomial Coefficient

65.

$$\binom{n}{k} = \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!}, \quad \binom{n}{n-k} = \binom{n}{k}$$

66.

$$\binom{n}{0} + \binom{n}{1} + \binom{n}{2} + \dots + \binom{n}{n} = 2^n$$

67.
$$\binom{n}{0} + \binom{n}{2} + \binom{n}{4} + \binom{n}{6} + \dots = 2^{n-1}$$

68.
$$\binom{k}{k} + \binom{k+1}{k} + \dots + \binom{n}{k} = \binom{n+1}{k+1}$$

69.
$$1 + 2 + 3 + \dots + n = \frac{n(n+1)}{2} = \binom{n+1}{2}$$

70.
$$n! \approx \left(\frac{n}{e}\right)^n \sqrt{2\pi n}$$

71.
$$\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)! = \sqrt{\pi}$$

72.
$$\binom{6}{3} = \binom{5}{2} + \binom{5}{3}$$

Complex Numbers

73.
$$z = a + bi, \quad (-i)^2 = i^2 = -1, \quad \frac{1}{i} = -i$$

74.
$$z = re^{i\theta} = r(\cos \theta + i \sin \theta)$$

75.
$$\sqrt{i} = \frac{1+i}{\sqrt{2}} = e^{\frac{i\pi}{4}}$$

Delta

76.
$$\delta[f(x) - f(x_0)] = \frac{\delta(x - x_0)}{|f'(x_0)|}, \quad \delta(ax) = \frac{1}{|a|}\delta(x)$$

77.

$$\delta_{mn} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{+\pi} e^{i(n-m)x} dx, \quad \delta(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{ixt} dt$$

78.

$$\delta(x) = -\frac{i}{\pi x} + \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{ixt} \Theta(t) dt$$

79.

$$\delta^3(\vec{x} - \vec{y}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{i\vec{p} \cdot (\vec{x} - \vec{y})} d^3p$$

80.

$$\delta(k - k') = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{i(k-k')x} dx$$

81.

$$\delta(x) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{+\infty} \cos(xt) dt, \quad \delta(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \cos(xt) dt$$

Exponential

82.

$$e = 1 + \frac{1}{1} + \frac{1}{1 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3} + \frac{1}{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4} + \dots$$

83.

$$e = 1 + \frac{1}{1!} + \frac{1}{2!} + \frac{1}{3!} + \dots$$

84.

$$e^x = 1 + \frac{x}{1!} + \frac{x^2}{2!} + \frac{x^3}{3!} + \dots$$

85.

$$a = e^k : a^x = e^{kx}$$

86.

$$e = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} = 2,71828\dots$$

87.

$$e^{ix} = \cos x + i \sin x, \quad e^{i\pi} + 1 = 0$$

88.

$$e^x = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n!}, \quad e = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^n = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} (1+x)^{1/x}$$

89.

$$e^x = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(1 + \frac{x}{n}\right)^n$$

90.

$$a^x = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(x \ln a)^n}{n!}$$

91.

$$\frac{\int \xi e^{\alpha \xi} d\xi}{\int e^{\alpha \xi} d\xi} = \frac{d}{d\alpha} \ln \int e^{\alpha \xi} d\xi$$

92.

$$\frac{d}{dx}(fg) = f \frac{dg}{dx} + \frac{df}{dx} g \quad \sim > \quad \int_a^b f \frac{dg}{dx} dx = - \int_a^b \frac{df}{dx} g dx + fg \Big|_a^b$$

Fibonacci

93.

$$1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 13, 21, \dots$$

94.

$$F_1 + F_2 + F_3 + \dots + F_n = F_{n+2} - 1$$

95.

$$F_1 + F_3 + F_5 + \dots + F_{2n-1} = F_{2n}$$

96.

$$\binom{n}{0} + \binom{n-1}{1} + \binom{n-2}{2} + \binom{n-3}{3} + \dots = F_{n+1}$$

97.

$$f_n = F_{n+1}, \quad f_{2n} = f_n^2 + f_{n-1}^2, \quad f_{m+n} = f_m f_n + f_{m-1} f_{n-1}$$

98.

$$1^2 + 1^2 + 2^2 + 3^2 + 5^2 + 8^2 + \dots + F_n^2 = F_n F_{n+1}$$

99.

$$F_{n+1} = F_n + F_{n-1}, \quad F_n^2 - F_{n-1}F_{n+1} = (-1)^{n+1}$$

100.

$$F_n^2 - F_{n-r}F_{n+r} = \pm F_r^2$$

101.

$$\text{gdc}(F_m, F_n) = F_{\text{gdc}(m,n)}$$

102.

$$g = \frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2} = 1.61803\dots, \quad \frac{1}{g-1} = g$$

103.

$$F_n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} \left[\left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2} \right)^n - \left(\frac{1 - \sqrt{5}}{2} \right)^n \right]$$

104.

$$g_+ = g, \quad g_- = \frac{1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}, \quad F_n = \frac{g_+^n - g_-^n}{\sqrt{5}}$$

Fourier

105.

$$\mathcal{F}\{f(x)\} = \tilde{f}(k) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(x) e^{-ikx} dx$$

106.

$$\mathcal{F}^{-1}\{\tilde{f}(k)\} = f(x) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \tilde{f}(k) e^{ikx} dk$$

107.

$$\mathcal{F}\left[\frac{d}{dx}f(x)\right] = ik\tilde{f}(k)$$

108.

$$\mathcal{F}\left[\vec{\nabla}f(\vec{r})\right] = i\vec{k}\tilde{f}(\vec{k})$$

109.

$$\mathcal{F} [\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{v}(\vec{r})] = i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{v}(\vec{k})$$

110.

$$\mathcal{F} [\vec{\nabla}^2 \psi(\vec{r})] = -k^2 \tilde{\psi}(\vec{k})$$

Fractions

111.

$$(b, d > 0) : \frac{a}{b} < \frac{a+c}{b+d} < \frac{c}{d}$$

112.

$$\frac{117}{25} = 4 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{2 + \frac{1}{8}}}$$

Function

113.

$$f(x) = f(x_0) + \frac{(x-x_0)}{1!} f'(x_0) + \frac{(x-x_0)^2}{2!} f''(x_0) + \dots$$

114.

$$f(a+x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n!} f^{(n)}(a) = f(a) + \frac{x}{1!} f'(a) + \frac{x^2}{2!} f''(a) + \dots$$

115.

$$(1+x)^q = 1 + qx + \frac{q(q-1)}{2!} x^2 + \dots + \frac{q(q-1)\dots(q-k+1)}{k!} x^k + \dots$$

116.

$$(1+x)^{1/2} = 1 + \frac{x}{2} - \frac{x^2}{8} + \frac{x^3}{16} - \frac{5x^4}{128} + \dots$$

117.

$$(1-x)^{1/2} = 1 - \frac{x}{2} - \frac{x^2}{8} - \frac{x^3}{16} - \frac{5x^4}{128} - \dots$$

118.

$$(1+x)^n = 1 + nx + \frac{n(n-1)}{2!} x^2 + \frac{n(n-1)(n-2)}{3!} x^3 + \dots$$

Gamma Function

119.

$$\Gamma(n) = (n - 1)!$$

120.

$$\Gamma(x + 1) = \int_0^{+\infty} t^x e^{-t} dt$$

121.

$$\Gamma(t) = \int_0^{+\infty} x^{t-1} e^{-x} dx$$

Geometry

122. triangle (sides a, b, c ; angle θ between b and c):

$$a^2 = b^2 + c^2 - 2bc \cos \theta$$

123. area S of a triangle (sides a, b, c):

$$S = \sqrt{s(s-a)(s-b)(s-c)}, \quad s = \frac{1}{2}(a+b+c)$$

124. triangle (sides a, b, c ; angle α between a and b):

$$c^2 = a^2 + b^2 - 2ab \cos \alpha, \quad S = \frac{ab \sin \alpha}{2}$$

125.

$$\int d\Omega_d = \frac{2\pi^{d/2}}{\Gamma(d/2)}$$

126.

$$V - E + F = 2$$

Green's Function

127.

$$G(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') = G(\vec{r} - \vec{r}'), \quad (\vec{\nabla}^2 + k^2) G(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') = -4\pi\delta(\vec{r} - \vec{r}')$$

Integral

128.

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\beta x^2} dx = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{\beta}}$$

129.

$$\int_0^{+\infty} x^n e^{-\beta x} dx = \frac{n!}{\beta^{n+1}}$$

130.

$$(n \neq m) : \int_0^{\pi} \sin(nx) \sin(mx) dx = \int_0^{\pi} \cos(nx) \cos(mx) dx = 0$$

131.

$$\int_0^{\pi} \sin^2(nx) dx = \int_0^{\pi} \cos^2(nx) dx = \frac{\pi}{2}$$

132.

$$\int \ln x dx = x \ln x - x + c$$

133.

$$\int_{-a}^a \frac{e^{ik(s-s')}}{2a} dk = \delta_{ss'}$$

134.

$$\operatorname{Re}(b) > 0 : \int_0^{+\infty} x^2 e^{-bx^2} dx = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{4b^{3/2}}$$

Logarithm

135.

$$\frac{d}{dx} \log x = \frac{1}{x} - i\pi\delta(x)$$

136.

$$a = \ln e^a, \quad a = e^{\ln a}$$

137.

$$\ln(1+x) = x - \frac{1}{2}x^2 + \frac{1}{3}x^3 - \frac{1}{4}x^4 + \dots$$

138.

$$(-1 < x \leq 1) : \ln(1+x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n+1} \frac{x^n}{n} = x - \frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{x^3}{3} - \frac{x^4}{4} + \frac{x^5}{5} - \dots$$

139.

$$1 - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{6} + \dots = \ln 2$$

Matrix

140.

$$\operatorname{tr}(AB) = \operatorname{tr}(BA), \quad \operatorname{tr} A^T = \operatorname{tr} A$$

141.

$$\operatorname{tr}(ABC) = \operatorname{tr}(CAB) = \operatorname{tr}(BCA)$$

142.

$$[A, B] = AB - BA, \quad \{A, B\} = AB + BA$$

143.

$$[A, BC] = [A, B]C + B[A, C]$$

144.

$$[A, BC] = \{A, B\}C - B\{A, C\}$$

Series

145.

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-s} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s}$$

146.

$$1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + \dots = -\frac{1}{12}$$

147.

$$1 - 2 + 3 - 4 + \dots = \frac{1}{4}$$

148.

$$1 - 1 + 1 - 1 + \dots = \frac{1}{2}$$

149.

$$1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + \dots = -\frac{1}{2}$$

150.

$$1 - \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{9} - \frac{1}{11} + \dots = \frac{\pi}{4}$$

151.

$$\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{16} + \frac{1}{32} + \dots = 1$$

152.

$$1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{8} + \dots + \frac{1}{2^n} = 2 - \frac{1}{2^n}$$

153.

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \dots \rightarrow \infty$$

154.

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = 1 + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{9} + \dots = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$$

155.

$$1^3 + 2^3 + 3^3 + \dots + n^3 = (1 + 2 + 3 + \dots + n)^2$$

156.

$$(x \neq 1) : 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + \dots + x^n = \frac{1 - x^{n+1}}{1 - x}$$

157.

$$(-1 < x < 1) : 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + \dots = \frac{1}{1 - x}$$

158.

$$\sum_{n=1}^k n = \frac{k}{2}(k+1), \quad (x \neq 1) : \sum_{n=1}^k x^n = \frac{x^{k+1} - 1}{x - 1}$$

159.

$$(|x| < 1) : \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} x^n = \frac{1}{1 - x}, \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{n}{(n+1)!} = 1$$

160.

$$(a + b)^N = \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{N!}{n!(N-n)!} a^n b^{N-n}$$

161.

$$(a + b)^N = \sum_{n=0}^N \binom{N}{n} a^n b^{N-n}$$

162.

$$\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{16} + \frac{1}{64} + \frac{1}{256} + \dots = \frac{1}{3}$$

163.

$$1 + \frac{i}{2} + \left(\frac{i}{2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{i}{2}\right)^3 + \dots = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{i}{2}}$$

164.

$$1 + 2 + 4 + 8 + 16 + \dots + 2^n = 2^{n+1} - 1$$

165.

$$1 + 2 + 4 + 8 + 16 + \dots = -1$$

166.

$$1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \dots + \frac{1}{n} \approx \gamma + \ln n, \quad \gamma = 0.5772155649\dots$$

167.

$$\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{11} + \frac{1}{13} + \dots \rightarrow \infty$$

168.

$$\sum_{n=1}^N \frac{1}{p_n} < 6, \quad p_n := \text{primes} < 10^{100}$$

169.

$$1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{4}} + \dots \rightarrow \infty$$

170.

$$\frac{1}{100} + \frac{1}{200} + \frac{1}{300} + \dots = \frac{1}{100} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \dots\right) \rightarrow \infty$$

171.

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = 1 + \frac{1}{2^2} + \frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{4^2} + \dots = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$$

172. $(p := \text{prime number}) : 1 + \frac{1}{2^p} + \frac{1}{3^p} + \dots < \frac{p}{p-1}$

173. $1 - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{16} - \dots = \frac{2}{3}$

174. $1 - x + x^2 - x^3 + x^4 - \dots = \frac{1}{1+x}$

175. $\frac{1}{3} = \frac{3}{10} + \frac{3}{10^2} + \frac{3}{10^3} + \dots$

176. $\frac{\pi}{4} = 1 - \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{7} + \dots$

Stokes' Theorem

177.
$$\int (\nabla \times \vec{F}) \cdot d\vec{s} = \oint \vec{F} \cdot d\vec{r}$$

Transfinite Numbers

178. $\omega = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}, \quad \epsilon_0 = \omega^{\omega^{\omega^{\omega^{\dots}}}}$

179. $\omega + 1 = \omega + 1 \neq 1 + \omega = \omega$

180. $\omega + n = \omega + n \neq n + \omega = \omega$

181. $\omega \cdot 2 = \omega + \omega, \quad 2 \cdot \omega = \omega, \quad n \cdot \omega = \omega$

182. $\omega \cdot \omega = \omega^2, \quad \omega^2 + \omega^2 = \omega^2 \cdot 2 \neq 2 \cdot \omega^2 = \omega^2$

Trigonometry

183.

$$e^{ix} = \cos x + i \sin x$$

184.

$$\sin x = \frac{1}{2i}(e^{ix} - e^{-ix}), \quad \cos x = \frac{1}{2}(e^{ix} + e^{-ix}), \quad \tan x = \frac{1}{i} \frac{(e^{ix} - e^{-ix})}{(e^{ix} + e^{-ix})}$$

185.

$$\sinh x = \frac{1}{2}(e^x - e^{-x}), \quad \cosh x = \frac{1}{2}(e^x + e^{-x}), \quad \tanh x = \frac{e^x - e^{-x}}{e^x + e^{-x}}$$

186.

$$\sin^2 x = \frac{1}{2}(1 - \cos 2x), \quad \cos^2 x = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \cos 2x)$$

187.

$$\sin^2 x + \cos^2 x = 1, \quad \cosh^2 x - \sinh^2 x = 1$$

188.

$$\sin(a \pm b) = \sin a \cos b \pm \sin b \cos a$$

189.

$$\cos(a \pm b) = \cos a \cos b \mp \sin a \sin b$$

190.

$$\tan(x \pm y) = \frac{\tan x \pm \tan y}{1 \mp \tan x \tan y}$$

191.

$$\sin^2\left(\frac{x}{2}\right) = \frac{1}{2}(1 - \cos x), \quad \cos^2\left(\frac{x}{2}\right) = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \cos x)$$

192.

$$\sin x = x \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{n^2\pi^2}\right), \quad \cos x = \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{4x^2}{(2n+1)^2\pi^2}\right)$$

193.

$$\sin^{-1} x + \cos^{-1} x = \frac{\pi}{2}$$

194.

$$\sin x = x - \frac{x^3}{3!} + \frac{x^5}{5!} - \frac{x^7}{7!} + \dots$$

195.

$$\cos x = 1 - \frac{x^2}{2!} + \frac{x^4}{4!} - \frac{x^6}{6!} + \dots$$

196.

$$\sin x = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n x^{2n+1}}{(2n+1)!}, \quad \cos x = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n x^{2n}}{(2n)!}$$

197.

$$\sinh x = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n+1}}{(2n+1)!}, \quad \cosh x = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n}}{(2n)!}$$

Open Invitation

*Review, add content to, and co-author this white paper [6, 7].
Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.*

Supplementary Files

[8]

How to Cite This White Paper

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+ **Zenodo**

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+ **OpenAI (GPT-4)**

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Agreement

All authors are in agreement with the guidelines presented in [7].

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References

- [1] Arfken, George B., Hans J. Weber, and Frank E. Harris. *Mathematical Methods for Physicists: A Comprehensive Guide*. Academic press, 2011.
- [2] Gradshteyn, Izrail Solomonovich, and Iosif Moiseevich Ryzhik. *Table of Integrals, Series, and Products*. Academic press, 2014.
- [3] Velleman, Daniel J. *How to Prove It: A Structured Approach*. Cambridge University Press, 2019.
- [4] Aigner, Martin, and Günter M. Ziegler. *Proofs from the Book*. Springer, 2018
- [5] Stillwell, John. *Roads to Infinity*. AK Peters, 2010.
- [6] Lobo, Matheus P. “Microarticles.” *OSF Preprints*, 28 Oct. 2019.
<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ejrct>
- [7] Lobo, Matheus P. “Simple Guidelines for Authors: Open Journal of Mathematics and Physics.” *OSF Preprints*, 15 Nov. 2019.
<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/fk836>
- [8] <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10901647>
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